

**STUDY ON VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF ROTOR BLADES
AND DAMPING SCHEME WITH FILM COOLING HOLES
UNDER ROTOR-STATOR INTERACTION**

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ABSTRACT

In this study, Sliding Mesh Model and Multiple Reference Frame Model are synchronously applied to simulate the relative motion of the static vanes and rotor blades of the first stage of E3 turbine, and the unsteady aerodynamic load on the blades and the vibration characteristics of the blades are analyzed using the fluid-structure interaction numerical calculation under both rated condition and off-design conditions. The calculation results indicate that under the situation of rotor-stator interaction, the unsteady aerodynamic load spectrum is close to the sinusoidal distribution, and the main load fluctuation frequency is equal to the frequency of the rotor blade passing through the stator vanes. When the unsteady aerodynamic load fluctuation frequency is approaching the blade's first modal frequency the blade vibration amplitude increases gradually. Especially, as the difference between the unsteady aerodynamic load fluctuation frequency and the blade natural frequency drops to less than 2.9%, the vibration damping ratio goes above 1 and the blade vibration diverges.

Then a damping scheme is proposed to suppress the vibrations caused by rotor-stator interaction in this paper. In this scheme, several rows of film cooling holes are arranged on the turbine shroud and they are located at the positions where the rotor blades bearing the maximum aerodynamic load. The calculation results show that the rotor blades will bear the unsteady aerodynamic loads from both the rotor-stator interaction and the film hole airflow of the shroud. The fluctuation amplitude of unsteady aerodynamic forces originating from the rotor-stator interaction is mitigated by 57.2% thanks to the effect of the shroud film holes. Thus the overall unsteady aerodynamic loads are stabilized. The criticality frequency difference of blade vibration divergence decreased from

2.9% to 1.4%. The maximum vibration stress of the blade drops from 9.7 MPa to 3.4 MPa under rated rotation speed. This damping scheme improves the safety margin of the gas turbine during start and stop as well as off-design operating conditions, and ultimately extending the rated service life of the turbine blade.

INTRODUCTION

The flow field characteristics periodically change over time because of the relative motion between the stationary vane rows and moving blade rows in a turbomachine. In the 1980s, numerical researches were carried out on rotor and stator interaction [1]. Giles [2] studied the transonic turbine and analyzed the shock wave and expansion wave acting on the blade in cascade channel. He et al. [3,4,5] proposed a series of schemes for numerical calculation of unsteady flow field under rotor-stator interaction and conducted studies of three-dimensional numerical calculations on multi-stage stators and rotors, which obtained more accurate and credible results. Generally, the rotor-stator interaction produces unsteady aerodynamic load acting on the blade. The vibration of turbine blades caused by the unsteady force is the main cause of high cycle fatigue failure of the blades. Moreover, when the frequency of the periodic change of unsteady aerodynamic force and the natural frequency of the blade are close, it would bring a strong resonance of the blade and the blade could be destroyed in a short time. Wagner [6], and Ma et al. [7] investigated the dynamic response of solid blades under unsteady aerodynamic loads and analyzed the stress and strain of the blades. It is worth attention that in such structural numerical studies, researchers often regard the unsteady aerodynamics as known conditions and focus on the solid calculations without considering the actual flow field. Joseph [8] studied

the rotor-stator interaction and the blade-forced vibration using the Euler/Navier-Stokes parallel solution method. Limited by the computational techniques of the time, such two-dimensional studies did not simulate and predict the real situation very suitably of the turbomachinery. With the gradual advancement of computing technology, the fluid-solid coupling numerical calculation is improved to meet the engineering requirements. Under such a background, this paper studied the unsteady aerodynamic forces and blades vibration characteristics under the rotor-stator interaction by using the fluid-solid coupling numerical calculation. Furthermore, an appropriate damping measure was developed to reduce the vibration of the blades and improve the reliability and prolong the life of the blades.

NOMENCLATURE

E	Young's modulus
G	Shear modulus
ν	Poisson's ratio
ρ	Density
t	Time
T	Period
f	Frequency
F	Force
p	Pressure
c	Chord
D	Displacement
σ	von Mises Stress

Subscripts

a	Axial direction
c	Circumferential direction
r	Radial direction

CALCULATION MODEL AND VERIFICATION

1) Model and numerical methods

In this paper, the first stage vanes and blades of E3 turbine are selected as study objects. The numerical method of fluid-solid coupling is applied to investigate the unsteady aerodynamic loads and vibration characteristics of the blades in the rotor-stator interaction flow environment. For the original E3 turbine, the numbers of the first stage full circle vanes and blades are 38 and 46, respectively. To simplify the calculation, the number of blades is adjusted to 76, and thus one vane and two blades form a corresponding relationship. Since the main purpose of this paper is to study the aerodynamic forces acting on the blades and their vibration characteristics, the cooling and heat exchange parts, including the film holes, the internal cooling structure, and the trailing edge splits of the blades, are simplified in the calculation. The fluid region is calculated using the commercial software ANSYS Fluent with a standard k- ϵ turbulence model. Table 1 gives the boundary conditions of the numerical calculation.

The fluid calculation region is divided with unstructured mesh. The thickness of the first prism mesh near the wall is 0.025 mm, and its y^+ value is near 30. The mesh-independent verification is performed by monitoring

change of the time-averaged value of pressure on the blade. Finally the mesh number 6.82 million is applied in the calculation under elements statistics. Figure 1 shows the fluid calculation region and mesh of the first stage.

Table 1 Boundary conditions of the fluid calculation

Item		Value
Inlet	Total pressure	2.526 MPa
	Total temperature	1780 K
	Turbulence intensity and scale	10%, 7.5 mm
Outlet	Static pressure	1.1227 MPa
Speed		12630 rpm

Fig. 1 First stage fluid calculation region and mesh

In the structural calculation, the film holes and the trailing edge splits are simplified but the blade's internal channels are retained. The blade root is fixed. The centripetal acceleration at the rated rotational speed is applied. The internal cooling channel applies a constant pressure of original coolant. The Hastelloy K405 used in the blade is an isotropic material, and its parameters are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Hastelloy K405 parameters

Property	Value
Young's modulus	173 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.29
Density	8120 kg/m ³
Thermal expansion coefficient	4.3×10 ⁻⁶ /K ⁻¹

Fig. 2 Blade structure calculation region and mesh

By monitoring the maximum stress and displacement of the blades during rotation, the mesh-independent tests have been performed to determine that the mesh number 0.34 million (elements statistics) is suitable for the numerical prediction and the final grid is shown in Fig 2. The structure dynamic of the solid part is calculated by software mechanical APDL (ANSYS Parametric Design Language). The fluid-solid coupling numerical calculations are carried out using Workbench System Coupling for data interchange and iterative solution.

2) Numerical method validation

In order to get the numerical results of fluid-solid coupling correctly, it is necessary to ensure that the fluid numerical calculation, the structural dynamics calculation and the data exchange between these two calculations are all exactly correct. However, it is hard to find the experimental data which is similar to this numerical study, as even at present it is very difficult to install the measuring components in high temperature and high speed rotating blades. Therefore, other experiment data are selected to verify the numerical method indirectly.

Firstly, the experimental data of the isentropic Mach number at different vane heights of the first stage of E3 turbine in the literature [9] are used to compare with the numerical results of this study. As shown in Fig. 3, the numerical results are in good agreement with the data of most experimental measuring points, and the difference is less than 5%. From Fig. 3 it can be considered that the calculation results of the flow field in the fluid-solid coupling calculation is accurate and credible.

Fig. 3 Surface static pressure comparison of numerical results and experiment

In addition, the numerical method of fluid-solid coupling in this paper is validated by comparing the aeroelastic wind tunnel experiments. It is the aeroelastic wind tunnel experiment of the AGARD 445.6 transonic wing in the 1960s American Langley Research Center [10]. By adjusting the inlet dynamic pressure at different Mach number, the vibration amplitude damping ratio of the swept wing was measured, and the dynamic pressure value of the critical flutter was found. In this experiment the

flutter data of multiple wing models at subsonic and transonic speeds had been tested, which are widely used in the verification of fluid-solid coupling method [11,12,13]. In this paper, the model of "weakened 3" wing is reconstructed. The airfoil of each section of the model is symmetrical wing type NACA65A004. The wing has a sweep angle of 45° at a quarter of a chord length, half wingspan of 0.762 m, shoot root ratio of 0.66, and mounting angle of 0°. The wing root is fixed. This study builds a fluid computation field around the wing with upper and lower 15 times geometric chord length, transverse 3 times wingspan and then divides it with the unstructured mesh. The fluid field mesh number is 4.11 million, and the solid domain grid is 0.07 million. The model and grid details are shown in Fig. 4. The wing material damping and structure damping are not considered in the numerical calculation as the measured values of the damping coefficient were not given in Reference [10].

Fig. 4 AGARD 445.6 Wing calculation model and mesh

Table 3 Equivalent material parameters of Weakened 3

Property	Value
Young's modulus	E_{11} 3.1511 GPa
	E_{22}, E_{33} 0.4162 GPa
Shear modulus	G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23} 0.4392 GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}$ 0.31
Density	ρ 377.2 kg/m ³

Fig. 5 Flutter Speed Index comparison of coupling numerical results and experiment

In the unsteady numerical calculation, the first-order torsional modal frequency of the wing is used as reference, and a calculation period is divided into 50 time steps and each time step is 5×10^{-4} s. In each time step, 200 steps are iterated, and during the iterations the fluid numerical calculation and the structural numerical calculation exchange data, wherein the numerical residuals of the node displacement and the force both fall below 0.01. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the non-dimensional parameter Flutter Speed Index between the experiment and numerical calculations.

The numerical results of Flutter Speed Index in this paper show the same trend as experiment data as well as those in other literatures. At transonic conditions the numerical result is slightly lower, but at subsonic conditions the numerical calculation is in good agreement with the experiment data. In addition, the whole first stage flow field environment of E3 is subsonic. It could be inferred that the numerical method in flow field calculation, structure calculation as well as data transfer between the two are consistent with the real situation. After the above verifications this numerical calculation method is applied to study the unsteady characteristics of the first stage vanes and blades of E3 gas turbine.

CALCULATION PROCESS AND RESULTS

1) Unsteady aerodynamic load calculation

The unsteady aerodynamic load of the blade is analyzed without considering the structure deformation at first. At the rated speed, a period of the blade sweep passing through one calculation region is 1.250×10^{-4} s. It is divided into 50 steps, each time step 2.50×10^{-6} s, and 40 iterations in each time step to ensure the residuals below 0.0001. The steady calculation result is used as the initialization field for the unsteady calculation. The unsteady aerodynamic load fluctuation on the blade is consistent after three period calculations.

Fig. 6 Axial load and circumferential load on the blade

The axial force and circumferential force on the surface of the blade for two periods after stabilization are plotted in Fig. 6. After passing through the vanes, the fluid exerts an unsteady load on the blade that is close to the sinusoidal distribution. The mean value of the circumferential force is 547.8 N, and the amplitude of vibration is 80.6 N.

Figure 7 shows the total pressure distribution and static pressure distribution of the vanes and blades interfaces at different times. The main flow of the cascade shows a higher total pressure distribution, while the wake of the stationary vanes exhibits a lower total pressure distribution.

Fig. 7 Total pressure of stator-rotor interface at different time

Fig. 8 Radial average static pressure along the circumferential distribution curve

Figure 8 gives a static pressure radial average curve, along with the circumferential distribution. Then a Fast Fourier Transform is made to the wave curve of different time, and the obtained spectrum picture is shown in Fig. 9. The frequency spectrum component of 7,999Hz has the maximal amplitude. This frequency is the same as the frequency at which the single blade is swept by the vanes. That is, the distribution of unsteady load is closely related to the wake and pressure environment of the upstream

stator vanes. When the suction surface of the blade is at a flow region where the pressure is lower than the mean value, and the pressure surface is in the high kinetic energy mainstream region where the pressure is higher than the mean value, the circumferential load on the blade reaches the maximum, and the opposite the minimum. The peak fluctuation is 14.7% of the average value.

Fig. 9 Fast Fourier Transform to static pressure

2) Coupling analysis under design conditions

The deformation of the blade structure resulting from the aerodynamic load is now considered for fluid-solid coupling calculations. The reason why the original single Slide Mesh Motion is not used in this study is that the blade cascade calculation region mesh nodes will be displaced once at every time step under the relative movement. The displacement is about 10 mm. However, the structural deformation causes the fluid calculation domain mesh displacement to be about 1×10^{-3} mm during the data exchange between fluid and solid. The final mesh node displacement is the sum of the two but these two displacements differ by several orders of magnitude and the small ones are swallowed up by the large ones. It would produce some errors in the calculation process. Therefore, this study proposes a new calculation scheme to simulate the interaction between blades and vanes. In the calculation, both the Frame Motion and the Slide Mesh Motion are applied to the vane domain synchronously. Only the Frame Motion is applied to the blade domain. The mesh nodes displacement of the blade domain in the calculation is only caused by the structural deformation. The actual rotation of the blade and the mutual interaction are simulated and calculated properly by this new scheme. The data transfer of the deformation is authentic and accurate.

Considering that the first stage blade has a low chord, the Smoothing Dynamic Mesh method in Fluent is adopted to the blade calculation domain, and the Spring Constant Factor is set to 0.8. The fluid calculation settings keep the same as the previous one only except that the iterations are increased from 40 to 200 in each time step. During these 200 iterations, the fluid calculation and the structural calculation exchanges data five times, and the numerical

residuals of the node displacement and the force are both drop below 0.01.

Figure 10 shows the maximum displacement curve and the maximum von Mises stress curve of the blade vibration during six periods. Fast Fourier Transform is performed on the time domain data of the total displacement and stress of the blade monitoring point. There are two peaks in Fig. 10, one is the first order vibration modal frequency of the blade 4,463Hz, and the other is the excitation frequency 7,999Hz generated by rotor and stator interference. Currently, the external excitation frequency is larger than the frequency of the first order vibration modal of the blade. The vibration of the blade is not obvious, and the maximum displacement of the blade tip is 2.83×10^{-2} mm, the maximum von Mises stress fluctuation amplitude is 9.7 MPa.

Fig. 10 Maximum displacement and maximum von Mises stress spectrum

3) Resonance analysis of off-design conditions

When the turbine rotational speed changes, the frequency of the single blade's being swept by the vanes also changes. If the external excitation frequency is close to the natural frequency of the blade, it is prone to resonance. In this paper, the fluid-solid coupling calculation is adopted to study the vibration of the blade under off-design conditions. As shown in Table 4, a total of five cases simulate the flow of the cascade and the vibration of blades at a rotational speed at which resonance easily occurs. In the calculation, in order to control the variable, the rotational speed is changed and the total pressure of the vane inlet is also changed to ensure that the time average load on the blade is unchanged. The total inlet pressure under different working conditions is also listed in Table 4.

Table 4 Rotational speed, boundary conditions and frequency in different calculation cases

Term	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Speed/(r·min ⁻¹)	7047	7258	7468	7680	7893
Inlet p _t /MPa	1.637	1.663	1.691	1.719	1.748
Frequency /Hz	4463	4597	4730	4864	4999
Difference	0%	3.01%	5.94%	8.95%	12.1%

After calculating a series of operating conditions, Fig. 11 shows the tip displacement vibration of the blade at different speeds. When the excitation frequency of the flow is the same as the natural frequency of the blade, the energy the blade obtained from the flow field increases rapidly, and the maximum von Mises stress reaches 577 MPa after 39 cycles, which exceeds the yield stress of K405 alloy at 1,270 K. It is considered that the blade vibration will be broken. For Case 3, when the difference between the airflow excitation frequency and the blade natural frequency is 5.94%, the maximum tip displacement is 0.08 mm and the overall damping ratio is less than 1, the blade is in a stable state at this condition. When the frequency difference continues to increase, the vibration displacement of the blade gradually becomes smaller, the damping ratio continues to decrease, and the blade vibration would not diverge. It should be pointed out that at working condition 2, although the overall damping ratio is less than 1, the blade vibration would not diverge, but the root of the blade bear an alternating stress of amplitude of 88.7 MPa, and the blade will be quickly fatigue and then failure.

Fig. 11 Blade tip vibration displacement under different rotation speed cases

DAMPING SCHEME WITH SHROUD FILM HOLES

1) Model of film holes damping scheme

In order to prevent the resonance of the turbine blade to ensure the stable working of the gas turbine, a series of measures have been proposed and applied, such as analyzing the Canberra diagram of the gas turbine, and then changing the blades' original stiffness or mass that the natural frequency of the blade or adjusting the number of blades, making sure that the blade natural frequency and excitation frequency are far away from each other to avoid resonance. Also, friction vibration damper lashing wires [14], shrouded structures [15], platform [16] etc have been provided. These mechanical damping dissipate the energy that the blade gets from the fluid to avoid resonance. All the above methods focus on the blade itself rather than the fluid excitation source. From the analysis of previous section, it can be concluded that the airflow excitation

force which the blades bearing spatially relates to the distribution of the stationary vanes. If some devices are installed on the stationary parts of the gas turbine to reduce the fluctuation amplitude or change the frequency of the airflow excitation force, it is expected to repress the vibration of the turbine blades.

The solution proposed in this paper is to arrange film holes on turbine shroud (casing), aiming at reducing the unsteady aerodynamic force fluctuation on the blade. The film holes distribution position is shown in Fig 12. The meridian plane cross section of the film hole is circular, and the hole diameter is 1.2 mm. The six film holes are arranged at the position on shroud where the blade bears maximum circumferential load. And the marshalling pattern of these holes is similar to the blade suction profile curve. The axis spacing between each film hole is 2.4 mm. With considering the limitations of machining and installation, the angle between the film hole and the local tangential plane of the shroud is taken as 45°, and the projection of the film hole on the meridional plane is 30° from the circumferential direction. The jet points to the blade suction surface. In this damping model the blade tip clearance remains the same as the original model 0.4 mm.

Fig. 12 Film holes distribution position on the shroud

The purpose of this arrangement is to ameliorate the impact of the jet on the blade, while taking into account in reducing the negative impact of the efficiency and the power output of the rotor.

In the calculation, the previous method is still applied. The flow field of the blade cascade domain is divided into two parts from the blade tip clearance. One part is the shroud and the film holes, which acting the same motion as the upstream stator. The other part is the blade cascade flow field without the shroud, which maintains the original motion of the blade as in the previous calculation. Referring to the previous grid-independent verification, the shroud and the film hole fluid domain mesh is generated by the same way. The mesh details of damping film holes on the shroud are shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Mesh of damping film holes on the shroud

The cooling air usage of these film holes is referenced to the original cooling air mass flow for cooling the first stage blade tip and shroud of the E3 turbine. The mass flow rate of cooling air for the single-row film holes is 0.004 kg/s. The total cooling flow of the whole cycle is 0.152kg/s, accounting for 0.24% of the mainstream, which is 39.7% of the original E3 cooling air flow. The total inlet pressure of the film hole is kept the same as the total pressure of the first stage vane inlet, which is 2.526 MPa. Here, the damping effect of the jet formation of the film holes is mainly considered, as the cooling and heat transfer is not the main object of this paper. For such study the film hole jet is set to the same temperature as the main flow of the cascade.

2) Film and comprehensive excitation force analysis

In order to independently explore the aerodynamic characteristics of the film holes jet to the blade, it is needed to rule out first the unsteady effects of the upstream vane row. The velocity field, pressure field and temperature field are time-averaged at the rotor and stator interface. One period is divided into 25 time steps at rated speed, each time step is 5.00×10^{-6} s, and 50 iterations in each time step. During the calculation process the circumferential forces of the surface of the blade are monitored as time goes on.

After four calculation periods, the circumferential force fluctuation in the two periods is shown in Fig. 14. The ordinate represents the percentage of the unsteady force because of the shroud film holes relative to the steady aerodynamic force, and the abscissa the period. The figure shows that unlike the unsteady aerodynamic load caused by the vane to the blade, the jet force of the film holes does not exhibit a distribution close to a sinusoidal wave. When the blade rotates and as it approaches the position of jet of the film holes, the reverse force of the jet acting on the blade gradually increases. That is, the circumferential load of the blade gradually decreases. After passing the extremum point of 0.69 T, the film hole reaches the position of the tip of the blade, and the jet of the film hole forms a good air seal effect, so that the circumferential force on the blade increases rapidly and even exceeds the time average value. However, due to the tip speed of the blade rotation of 483.1 m/s, the time of the

film holes staying at the tip of the blade is short. The air seal effect disappears quickly, and the circumferential force of the blade is reduced. The original film holes are arranged according to the profile curve of the suction surface of the blade. The film holes gradually deviate from the profile curve of the pressure surface of the blade when leaving the top of the blade, and finally completely get away from the moving blade, thus causing the circumferential load of the blade staged down. Then this will be repeated from the beginning into the next period. In an overall way, the unsteady aerodynamic forces fluctuation formed by the jet of gas film holes and the unsteady aerodynamic forces fluctuation formed by the stator and rotor interaction are in opposite phase.

Fig. 14 Damping film circumferential load spectrum

Next, the comprehensive aerodynamic characteristics of the shroud film holes jet and the upstream vane interaction to the blade are studied. The calculation remains the same settings and boundary conditions as the previous.

Fig. 15 Load spectrum comparison of original model and improved model with film damping scheme

The circumferential force in the two periods after stabilization is shown in the black curve in Fig. 15. Under the joint action of the vane and the film holes, the circumferential load on the blade is not the original wave likely sinusoidal distribution. It becomes the superposition of two waveforms with smaller amplitude and higher

frequency. The maximum amplitude of the improved circumferential load fluctuation is reduced by 57.2% compared to the original one. As a result, it is expected to reduce the energy that the blade gets from the fluid, thereby suppressing the vibration of the blade under the influence of the upstream stationary vanes.

3) Vibration and film damping effect

Figure 16 shows the vibration of the blade under the combined action of the vane and the film holes at the rated speed. The maximum stress appears at the root of the trailing edge. The amelioration is that the maximum stress is reduced from 9.7 MPa to 3.4 MPa compared to the original model. The maximum displacement of the tip is reduced from 2.83×10^{-2} mm to 2.24×10^{-2} mm.

Fig. 16 Maximum displacement and maximum von Mises stress spectrum under combined action

Fig. 17 Comparison of unsteady load between mainstream and shroud film

Although the jet of the film hole has a reverse load on the moving blade with fluctuation amplitude of only 6.56% which is far less than the aerodynamic excitation force of the vane of 14.23%, but the action position on the blade of these two kinds of force is different. As shown in Fig. 17, compared with the mainstream force action in the middle blade span, the flows of the film holes are close to the tip of the blade, and the torque arm of the film streams force on the blade root is longer than that of the mainstream. So the film flows can play a significant role in reducing the excitation force generated by the stator-rotor interaction.

Finally, for the off-design conditions, the five operating conditions in Table 4 have also been calculated, and then the results of the vibration of the blades near the resonance point obtained. The vibration displacement of blade tip is shown in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18 Blade tip vibration displacement under different rotation speed cases with film damping

From Fig. 18 it can be seen that at the resonance point, compared to the original model, the energy obtained from the fluid in each of the vibration cycles of the blade under the shroud film damping scheme is greatly reduced. In Case 2, the amplitude of the alternating stress at the root of the blade is reduced from 88.7 MPa to 36.0 MPa. For Case 3, when the difference between the airflow excitation frequency and the blade natural frequency is 5.94%, the maximum tip displacement is reduced to 0.033 mm compared to the original model, and the overall damping ratio is less than 1. When the frequencies continue to move away from each other, the blade vibration displacement continues to decrease, and the blade is in a stable state and does not vibrate to diverge. From the above discussion it could be found that the damping scheme of the shroud film holes effectively reduces the alternating stress and displacement near the resonance point and improves the safety margin of the gas turbine under off-design conditions.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents a fluid-structure interaction numerical study to the first stage of E3 turbine and analyzes the unsteady aerodynamic load and the vibration of the blades under rotor-stator interaction environment. In view of the unsteady aerodynamic characteristics, this study proposes a damping scheme that arranges the film holes on the turbine shroud corresponding to the blade to weaken the excitation force produced by stator rotor interaction, and performs coupling calculation on this damping scheme. The following conclusions are obtained:

1) Because of the wake and pressure environment by the upstream stator vanes, the fluid exerts an unsteady load

on the first stage blade that is close to the sinusoidal distribution. The frequency of this unsteady load is the same as the frequency of which the single blade is swept by the vanes, and its phase also accords with the relative position of the blade and vane.

2) When the gas turbine is working under off-design conditions, especially the frequency of rotor and stator interaction excitation force is close to the natural frequency of the blade, the blade appears serious resonance. When the difference between the two frequencies is within 2.9%, the vibration would diverge.

3) The unsteady aerodynamic force produced by turbine shroud (casing) film holes does not completely exhibit a sinusoidal distribution to the moving blade. The phase of the unsteady load from the film holes is opposite to the excitation force of rotor-stator interaction. The original airflow excitation force focus on the blade from the upstream static vanes is reduced by 57.2%. The criticality frequency difference in the vibrational divergence of the blade decreased from 2.9% to 1.4%. At the rated speed of the turbine, the maximum vibration stress of the blade is reduced from 9.7 MPa to 3.4 MPa.

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